

A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE SPHERES OF SCRUTINY

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15299807

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Bachelor's degree in Literature. Post-Doctorate in Social Psychology. E-mail:

srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the theme of the spheres of scrutiny, in an attempt to make a phenomenological interpretation of their origin and existence and how they represented enormous relevance for the life, existence, death and destiny of individuals and entire nations, surviving to the present day, under a determining symbolic aspect. This is a bibliographical research, based on epic, classical and historical studies, until reaching a condition of deep interpretation, a description and a synthesis that allows to clarify, from a semantic understanding, their influence on modern thought, keeping alive a tradition and the reminiscences of a time. The objective of this essay is to understand how the spheres of scrutiny interfere in the maintenance of harmony and agreement among members of initiatory orders. The spheres of destiny were so called because they were responsible for determining the good or bad luck of an individual in moments of crisis, that is, the fate between life and death would be decided through them and the decision would be final, because the choice was beyond the possibility of any human intervention in the process. Nowadays, the secret ballot regarding the fate of the candidates is more open, a change in the process and, if the distributor of the spheres is perceptive enough, he or she will be able to know which of the judges voted for or against the candidate. It is concluded that, with the development of human thought and its distancing from the mysticism that marked the beginning of its existence, the power of hidden beings was suppressed and, along with it, the belief in the inexorability of Destiny, which caused subjectivity to arise in place of such superstition, the freedom to judge the causes according to one's own understanding of the causal link understood about human relations marked by all types of conflict.

Keywords: Stones of Destiny. Spheres of scrutiny. Trial of Orestes. Semantic analysis. Phenomenological interpretation.

INTRODUCTION

The spheres of scrutiny were once, in ancient times, called *stones of destiny*, and not only because they determined the meaning and course of the life of the one whose life was judged based on his choices; it was because they were under the judgment of destiny, of luck.

The judge selected a sphere not according to his individual judgment; it was justice that judged the defendant under accusation and if he was innocent, the stone would be white and, otherwise, the stone would be black.

What is currently classified as luck or bad luck, or even chance, was what determined someone's freedom, slavery, life or death. Many accused people were acquitted of their crimes and many innocent people were punished, because their defenses were directed to human judges; however, those who would make the judgments were invisible forces, completely outside the control of humans and the gods.

This condition of judgment represented a kind of ordeal ²used by the Greeks for many centuries, until it was abolished at the time of the great revolution in which the dominion of the Polis passed from the hands of the matriarchy to the patriarchy, a moment marked by the *Trial of Orestes*, accused of the crime of matricide, for killing his own mother, in revenge for her having plotted against his father, together with his brother-in-law and having killed him; however, after having committed this act, he began to be persecuted by the Erinyes ³, Alecto (*Ἀληκτώ*, the implacable), in charge of punishing moral crimes such as anger, rage and pride. She followed the offender without stopping, threatening him with lit torches, not letting him sleep in peace. Megaera (*Μέγαιρα*, the spiteful one), who personifies rancor, envy, greed and jealousy. She punishes mainly crimes against marriage, especially infidelity; she shouts incessantly in the ear of the criminal, reminding him of the faults he has committed. Tisiphone (*Τισιφώνη*, the avenger), the avenger of murders (patricide, fratricide, homicide); she scourges the guilty and drives them mad.

This turning point in the history of humanity is a paradox, because whoever committed a bloody crime had to atone for it in the same measure, that is, blood was paid with blood and, quite possibly, until this specific trial, all the others were nothing more than mere figurative situations in order to make people believe that there was some kind of justice in favor of the criminal or that he was given an opportunity to save himself from a cruel and bloodthirsty fate. Pallas Athena, by deciding in favor of Orestes (as a defendant) did not affront fate; but rather a

² The ritual called *ordeal* is a judicial test, in general, with the objective of proving the guilt or innocence of the accused. Also known as the judgment of God (*judicium Dei*, in Latin), it is a type of ancient judicial test, used to determine the guilt or innocence of the accused through the participation of elements of nature and whose result is interpreted as a divine judgment (ARTUSO, Vicente. The violence of the ordeal against the woman suspected of adultery in NM 5,11-31. *Perspect. Teol.*, Belo Horizonte, v. 53, n. 3, p. 649-670, Set./Dec. 2021, p. 649).

³ The Erinyes (Greek : *Ἐρινύες*), in Greek mythology, were personifications of vengeance. While Nemesis (goddess of vengeance) punished the gods, the Erinyes punished mortals. They were Tisiphone (Punishment), Megaera (Grudge) and Alecto (Unnameable).

system that was shown to be unjust and merciless; therefore, imperfect, because it did not consider the intrinsic and unconscious motivations of the accused.

The fate given to the accused, through the spheres of destiny, was a surreal condition, because the jury member was not even given the possibility of deducing a condition of acquittal from his own judgment, since the spheres, black and white, were mixed together, giving the individual no power of choice. If his individual consideration coincided with the color of the sphere, it was because it was determined that way and his judgment was correct; however, if it was the opposite, conflicting his judgment with the selected stone, it proved that he was wrong, and he might or might not have to live with the guilt of having condemned an innocent person to death or exile or a guilty person to full acquittal. All human life was subject to chance, to the risk of a judgment that could be fair or unfair.

By taking such power from the hands of destiny, the Most Serene Goddess Pallas Athena transfers to men all responsibility for their judgments regarding their fellow citizens. This was the first step towards allowing human beings to experience the taste of their free will in relation to their existence, leaving behind in the very recent past their condition as prisoners of the [*always volatile and dubious*] moods of the gods, whom they feared more than death itself. From this event onwards, the spheres of destiny began to be called spheres of scrutiny, which still remained a secret act in order to preserve the suitability of each member of the judgment committee.

Nowadays, it is a purely symbolic act, since the individual subjected to such judgment is judged according to the subjectivity of each judge, who has the conscious principle that he is judging him according to his own doctrine and values, which may or may not be in accordance with the society of which he is a part; without going into the particular merits of who or what is right or wrong.

THE TRIAL OF ORESTES

The Trial of Orestes is a very strange and complex chapter in the history of humanity, in which the saga begins with a religious conflict that occurred during the siege of the city of Troy, a time when they were at war, because of the kidnapping of Helen and an eagle [*Symbol of Zeus*] killed a pregnant rabbit [*animal protected by Artemis*] and, in retaliation for the attack, the hunting goddess asked for a blood sacrifice, which led Agamemnon to sacrifice his own daughter, being saved by Achilles who fell in love with the young woman. As revenge for

having attempted against the life of her own daughter, Clytemnestra kills him, counting on the help of her brother-in-law, who became her lover.

Iphigenia plots retaliation against her mother and convinces Orestes to sacrifice her as revenge for her father's death. However, after carrying out the crime, which should be seen and recognized as an act of justice, he begins to be persecuted by the Erinyes, a neurotic complex of guilt, and this is the turning point in which he remains obscure, because if that were the case, there would be no reason to feel guilty about his actions; which reveals that matriarchy still represented an immense force over society, education, customs and tradition.

The point that remains unclear and that we intend to shed light on here is that the death of the father was something so serious that it deserved retaliation and, in the same proportion, the death of the mother was the target of an epic trial and judgment, presided over by a god and accompanied by several others, which reveals that the powers between the father and the mother were in balance [*not harmonious*]. On the one hand, Orestes was exalted for his bravery; on the other, he was hunted and condemned for his cowardice and blasphemous act. However, he and his attitude only became the pivot of a situation that had been dragging on for a long time and for which society could not find a plausible solution.

Greek society was undergoing an intense transformation, in which men were taking control of everything; however, women still held immense power, caused by the superstitious fear that had been created around them and their attributes in very distant eras. However, with political growth and the demands of commercial agreements, existence began to take on other forms, causing members of the male sex to assume increasingly higher positions in the command of the Polis and in the most complex decisions.

For a certain period, both groups lived in a relative state of peace and respect for each other, until the death of a father by a woman threw their coexistence into disarray, and they had to find balance through a blood trial, which could only be carried out by a male member. Orestes was chosen and, contrary to popular belief, the power of women was still far superior to that of men, and the situation became uncontrollable, demanding a punishment worthy of the heinous criminal; however, if this were accepted, it would demonstrate that they still held absolute control, although they remained silent.

Thus, the Most Serene Goddess Pallas Athena established the Court of Athens, built on the mountain of Ares, the god of War, and which, for this reason, was given the name Areopagus⁴, where the individual accused of legitimate transgression, Orestes, for the crime of matricide,

⁴The *Areopagus* was a council of members of the Athenian aristocracy, whose duties, as an instance of the different types of government that Athens had undergone, changed over time. Among its members, some were invariably

would be judged by the State. With this, there was already an enrage of those who represented the feminine power over the Polis, because the fact that a blasphemous act like that could be defended before a court could already be considered a sacrilegious act, with even the most remote possibility that he would be acquitted of his horrendous crime, this frightened them because it would represent their loss of absolute control over social thought. It is clear that what was at stake was something that was far beyond the guilt or innocence of Orestes; this only served as a purpose to define a social aspect that would determine the course of Greek civilization from then on, affecting its customs and traditions.

The court is created and established with its first case being a blood trial, in which a man is brought to trial for having murdered a woman and, note that the fact that he had also killed a man is not brought up at the time. Twelve judges are summoned, representing the 12 tribes of Athens and, occasionally, at the end of Orestes' argument, in which he presents his defense, with none other than Phoebus Apollo as his defense attorney, the decision ends in a tie, not by subjective definition on the part of the judging authorities; but by force of the very convenience of Fate, which remains in doubt about the guilt or innocence of the young accused. "--- Orestes, son of Agamemnon and Clytemnestra!" said the goddess Athena, standing up at the top of the platform. --- You are now before the twelve judges of this Areopagus to answer the accusation of having cruelly killed your own mother."

What is interesting to note here is that the young man's fate is no longer determined by the decision of the sunset, since the choices of the spheres that would condemn or acquit him were already under the subjective judgment of the judges in question. A tie was reached, and was decided by the vote of the goddess who presided over the court. This leads to an interpretation that doubts hung over the administrative model of that historical moment, in which men and women shared responsibilities and, consequently, power. None of the judges present there were concerned with the death of a woman or the conviction of a man; their concerns focused on the control of the city, on how power would be distributed after that incident.

The acquittal of Orestes by the Court of Ares officially determined the end of matriarchy in Greece and, consequently, consolidated the implementation of the patriarchal regime. Only

chosen to receive the title of archon (a type of "king" or "ruler"), each responsible for a different aspect of the government of Athens. The name "areopagus" is an adaptation of *areopagus* (or *Areios Pagos*, from "Ἄρειος πάγος"), which means something like "Hill of Ares", in reference to the Greek god of war. This reference is due to the fact that the members of the Areopagus, as aristocrats, generally fulfilled the role of elite warriors in times of war, responsible for the protection of the city. In the democratic period, the Areopagus fulfilled the function of a court constituted by archons who were responsible for judging crimes of premeditated murder, poisoning and arson, among others.

under absurd pressure were women able to maintain their *status quo* in society, with men fearing a revolution by them and a consequent loss of their power, conquered through intense struggle and bloodshed. The trial did not determine the guilt or innocence of a man; the political future of a nation was at stake and, after its conclusion, it set a precedent for the creation of a democratic regime, with the creation of the judiciary, which would act as a moderating power from then on, not allowing either the practice of tyranny or the practice of anarchy.

THE SPHERES OF DESTINY

The *spheres of destiny* were so called because they were responsible for determining the good or bad luck of an individual in moments of crisis, that is, the fate between life and death would be decided through them and the decision would be final, because the choice was beyond the possibility of any human intervention in the process. It was a set of white spheres and a single black sphere, all placed in a single bag and distributed to the participants in the action until the one who accidentally took the black sphere would be chosen for the sacrifice, regardless of its dimension, which ranged from receiving special training, to becoming a hieroglyph or to being a victim in some sacrificial ritual in honor of a god or to calm the fury of these.

This condition was used at a time in human history when the science of probability was not yet available as an instrument to interfere in decision-making; everything was decided by the supreme will of *Physis*, the condition of *Destiny already existed*, in which from the height of its infinite distance, unreachable to human beings, without any conditions to provoke interference and without being able to appeal, since the Moiras were above even the will of the gods and Zeus himself.

It is observed that this historical moment represents a moment of transition between religious arbitrariness and the scientific determination of things, with the belief that events are occasional and that some individuals were chosen even before they were born for certain missions and/or privileges or even heroic sacrifices. The jurors did not know which sphere their hands would take; they were guided by the most complete sunset, without being able to infer any thought or individual value judgment in the decision that occurred there, leaving no room for the chosen one to complain; in fact, if he or anyone else dared to attempt this direction, the punishment was very severe, since what was being decided there, at that moment, was, in general, the well-being and even the survival of the entire community.

Over the centuries, the stones of destiny arbitrarily decided the lives and fortunes, as well as the misfortunes of all participants, and there was no way to appeal the decision, as it was final. In preparation for Orestes' trial, the Goddess Pallas Athena changed the rules and allowed that, while maintaining the tradition of secret voting and absolute secrecy regarding the individual decision on the case and the subject of the trial, each judge could vote according to his or her own deliberations, understanding and interpretation of the accused.

Voting, using the stones of destiny, becomes a symbolic act, respecting tradition and maintaining a security mechanism for the participants in the decision, in which it would not be known who had voted for or against. However, the condition of subjectivity is established here, in which the decision about someone's future is taken from the hands of the dark and inexorable Destiny and placed in the hands of men who would judge according to their own consciences and feelings what, in the Goddess's conception, was the fairest [*or even the least unfair*] way of deciding about a man's life.

When the verdict on Orestes' guilt is revealed to be inconclusive, the epic speech of the President of the Court reveals the instrument in question that was *sub judice* , claiming that it was in favor of the father and that she cared little about a woman who had been killed and that, from now on, as the court had not reached a conclusive verdict, being in doubt as to the object of judgment, that it should favor the defendant, thus becoming an instrument of law from that moment on.

As the twelve Athenian citizens cast their votes in the ballot box, the goddess of Justice clarifies: “I will be the last to cast my vote. And I will add them to those in favor of Orestes. I was born without having passed through a mother’s womb; my spirit has always been in favor of men, except in marriage; I support the father. Therefore, I have no major concern for a wife who killed her husband, the guardian of the home; for Orestes to win, it is enough that the votes are divided equally” (ATHENA).

There is silence. Given the anxiety of all present, there is a pause. The goddess gives her verdict: “This man is acquitted of the crime of matricide because the number of votes is equal on both sides.” There is something more important at stake in this court *in dubio pro reo* , in this court of justice and not of vengeance.

When the voting was over, Athena finally began to remove the balls from the urn. Six times her hand picked up white balls. And six times she picked up black balls. “The judges have not reached an agreement,” the Goddess announced laconically. Orestes, distressed, did not know what to say or what to expect. The Erinyes spread their black wings and sang their frightening hymn, in which they called for the cruelest punishment. Athena the Just then

decided to cast the decisive vote herself: “My vote will be final,” she said, looking sternly at everyone, “and woe to anyone who dares to use harsh words to contest it!” The goddess climbed the steps to the urn and secretly cast her solitary vote before it. Then one of the judges was called to take the vote and proclaim the sentence.

--- Athena, Goddess of Wisdom and Justice, supreme magistrate of this court, now decides for the acquittal of the accused! - said the judge at last, taking the fatal ball from the urn. --- It seems that the cruel era of savage punishments and terrible expiations is finally coming to an end - said Apollo to the Erinyes, his face shining.

This stance taken by the Most Serene and Enchanting Goddess of Justice and Wisdom allows us to deduce that in other cases of trial there were indecisions regarding the guilt of the accused and, in this case, they were subjected to a condemnatory judgment. The law of matriarchy was very severe and acted with the sole intention of punishing everyone with the utmost severity. It is no wonder that the Greeks lived from then on in fear of its return.

THE SPHERES OF SCRUTINY

As already explained in another topic, on the occasion of Orestes' trial, the Goddess Pallas Athena changes the rules on the use of the *stones of destiny*, as a form of judgment on the accused, thus making them merely scrutiny stones, a way of maintaining secrecy about the conscious decision of the jury members; but, the judgment already becomes something based on subjectivity, that is, each one was free to deliberate according to their understanding of the causal link revealed during the process.

Nowadays, the secret ballot regarding the candidates' fate is carried out in a more open manner, a change in the process and, if the distributor of the balls is perceptive enough, he/she can know which of the judges voted for or against the candidate. The correct form of voting in this sense should be carried out in a private room, where the two bags of balls, respectively the white and the black ones, are arranged and there, in a completely equitable manner, the choice should be made based on their intrinsic deliberations, depositing in the ballot box the one that they have determined, without having to obtain any explanation, maintaining the tradition, in which it was destiny that decided on the candidate, considering that we are referring to traditional societies and that their members seek to preserve as much as possible the principles defended by them since primitive times.

In primitive societies, where human beings were governed almost exclusively by superstition and fear of the wrath of the gods, manifested through natural phenomena, the choice

of those who would receive the mission of calming the fury of the gods fell to a member of the ruling family, generally the firstborn or the eldest daughter of the priest, depending on the hidden interests of each proposer. As the power of royal families increased, strategies began to be created that could reduce the risk of their children being murdered, without having to resort to trickery and methods of deception against the gods.

This is how the choice is born, submitted to the stones of destiny, having to first transform it into an extremely powerful, inexorable god, to whom one could not appeal his decision, because everything had already been planned before each individual was even born. It was following this tradition that mythological tales were created and the plot around them constructed, in which the destiny planned for someone, whether glorious or disastrous, would be fulfilled to the letter.

In Antiquity, although subjectivity was born and imposed in the trial of Orestes, as a condition for issuing judgments, it would take many centuries for it to become a condition of experience imposed in courts, where jury members still resorted to *physical manifestations* before making their final decisions about the fate of the accused and/or for the acceptance of future members of their associations. These revelations were linked to the judge's thinking about the decision he should make; for example, if, by chance, he believed that the accused was innocent, he would ask his protective god to send him some kind of message, some kind of sign, and if he was not given even a small sign, it was proof that he was wrong in his judgment; thus, he would vote against what he had been defending up until that moment.

With this, the stones of destiny no longer determined the fate of the individual, becoming an adornment to be used to satisfy a design of tradition. With the advancement of science and humans moving further and further away from their beliefs in the forces of nature, no longer seeking phenomenological signs that could guide them in their decisions, they began to decide matters deliberately, at most, taking them in accordance with the ideologies and beliefs of the group, that is, influenced by its members.

The spheres of scrutiny still exist and their use persists in more complex situations involving more serious decisions between groups; when, in fact, all votes should follow the parameters of absolute secrecy regarding the subjective deliberation of the participants, leaving under suspicion even the vote of the person who expressed himself, exposing his opinions and precepts about the object of judgment.

This disentanglement of tradition is a dangerous aspect, because it leads to the fear that, at any moment, this situation will be abolished from the codex of fraternities that seek to remain as faithful as possible to the old ways of working and acting in accordance with their principles

and values. The ideal would be to return to the more rigid models of application of their molds during all moments in which there is a need to decide on something, no matter how simple the situation may seem, because this would lead to an understanding that once a decision is made, there is no way to regret it, and this feeling, if it becomes part of the participant in the action, should be maintained as something that is part of their innermost being, not a subject of deliberate and open discussion.

Thus, the spheres of scrutiny survive as part of the tradition in the great initiatory societies, although with a very limited dimension in relation to their use in late and classical Antiquity, and even more so in relation to their intrinsic value of ethical responsibility. This is the main question that arises when faced with the need to make decisions that go beyond a simple act of judging a situation or someone, in which this process can determine the course of the life of one or many individuals.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

What we sought to consider in this essay is how the stones of destiny are relegated to mere symbolic spheres in an act of scrutiny that, if due care is not taken, will no longer be the holders of the secrets that, in their primitive times, they carried with such effusion and prestige for being so. The act, which in its origin expressed a condition of absolute power of Destiny over the lives of humans, is transmuted, in the present day, into a reminiscence of tradition, a symbolic act.

The stones of destiny were responsible for deciding the life, death and existence of countless individuals as well as entire nations, whose fate was decided by the wrathful gods, through the simple condition that among all those miserable profane beings to be judged, destiny determined the existence of a single just person and, not infrequently, they decided in favor of all, due to the fate of just one.

With the development of human thought and its distancing from the mysticism that marked the beginning of its existence, the power of hidden beings was being suppressed and along with them, the belief in the inexorability of Destiny, which caused subjectivity to emerge in place of such superstition, the freedom to judge the causes according to one's own understanding of the causal link understood about human relations marked by all types of conflict.

The birth of subjectivity and its permission for deliberate use was the first step towards the emergence of Democracy in Greece and, from then on, what remained of the stones of

destiny as historical elements was the fact that their maintenance during the most difficult trials would keep secret the way in which each member of the jury had voted in the decisions. This meant a lot for future societies, especially those that seek to remain faithful to traditions, where harmony and concord are highly valued and preserved values.

During the Trial of Orestes, the Most Serene Goddess of Wisdom and Justice, Pallas Athena, kept the voting pattern secret for all the judges, for fear of reprisals by the Erinyes against those who, by deliberate decision, had voted in favor of the accused, revealing only their vote, against which the virgins of vengeance could do nothing, for fear of the wrath of Olympian Zeus.

Of all the changes that have occurred in relation to them, a reminiscence has survived to this day that many refuse to seek out and analyze, without understanding that it was not always this way. And, a deep and broad study of their origins and transformations is shown to be something of extreme necessity so that, at a time not too distant in the future, they will be considered as something to be abolished from the sacred and ritualistic liturgy of many of the classical societies that still preserve tradition as their pillar.

From *Stones of Destiny* and how powerful this expression is, they have come to be considered as mere *Spheres of Scrutiny*, a symbol that, given the semantic distance that separates those interested in knowledge, does not express any epic, classical or historical meaning for the initiatory orders. It is necessary to restore their emblematic force that represents their responsibility for the maintenance of the cosmic order.